

Usual and unusual reactions of platinum complexes^ψ

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Contents

1. Introduction
2. Interaction of platinum complexes with DNA
3. Kinetics and mechanism
 - (i) Complexation of [Pt(dien)(H₂O)]²⁺ with nucleobases
 - (ii) Reaction of chloro- and aqua(diethylethylamine)platinum(II) with model nucleosides
 - (iii) Complexation of *trans*-[PtCl₂(NH₃)₂] with model nucleobases
 - (iv) Reaction with amino acids and its analogues
 - (v) Formation of oxo and Pt⁰ complexes
 - (vi) Oxidation of SO₂ by platinum complexes
4. Luminescence properties
5. Ligand isomerism and stacking in square planar platinum complexes
6. Conclusion
7. References

1. Introduction

In the last four decades much attention has been focussed on the discovery of drug candidates exhibiting antineoplastic properties. The *cis*-diamminedichloroplatinum(II), commonly known as *cisplatin* discovered by Rosenberg *et al.* in 1965¹, is accepted worldwide as one of the most potent chemotherapeutic agent in the treatment of a variety of tumors, particularly against testicular, bladder, prostate, ovarian and cervical carcinomas² and against squamous cell carcinoma of head and neck as well as sarcomas and melanomas³. Its therapeutic activity is considered to be due to its interaction with DNA resulting in inhibition of DNA synthesis⁴. The most preferred reaction in this case, both *in vivo* and *in vitro*, involves loss of two Cl⁻ ions resulting in *cis*-diaquadiamineplatinum(II); this Pt^{II} species coordinates to the N7 atoms of adjacent guanine bases on the same strand of DNA by aqua ligand displacement⁵. *Cisplatin* uniquely forms the intrastrand adducts of types GG, AG and GXG^{6(a)} whereas the inactive *trans* isomer of this ana-

logue does not link to adjacent guanine bases but forms intrastrand adducts having one or more intervening nucleotide(s)^{6(b)}. The treatment by *cisplatin* is complicated due to its concentration-dependent nephrotoxicity⁷ and other cytotoxic effects such as hair loss, anemia, impairment of taste and hearing senses, and also nausea and vomiting⁸. To overcome this limitation the search for other analogs of *cisplatin*, with reduced cytotoxicity and similar and/or improved therapeutic properties, has been under active investigation. Carboplatin (*cis*-(diammine)(1,1-cyclobutanedicarboxylato)platinum(II) and iproplatin (*cis*-dichloro-*trans*-dihydroxo-*cis*-bis-(isopropylamine)platinum(IV) are considered as the successful second generation antitumor drugs which exhibit higher degree of myelotoxicity⁹ but less reactive properties than *cisplatin*. A series of platinum complexes with phosphonic acid ligands were synthesized and tested against various carcinoma cell lines¹⁰. It has been found that these complexes exhibit therapeutic activity *in vivo* by reduction of the bone tumor volume and

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

antimetastatic activity¹¹. The *cis*-[Pt(NH₃)₂(ntmp)] (ntmp = nitrilotris(methylenephosphonic acid)) has been reported to be as effective as *cis*platin in osteosarcoma but relatively less toxic¹². Recently a number of articles on anticancer activities of platinum complexes have appeared in the literature¹³. The structures of *cis*platin (**1**), *trans*platin (**2**), carboplatin (**3**), iproplatin (**4**), and *cis*-[Pt(NH₃)₂(ntmp)] (**5**), [Pt-(*R,S*-dach)(ntmp)] (dach = diaminocyclohexane) (**6**) are presented in Chart 1.

Chart 1

2. Interaction of platinum complexes with DNA

Many investigations have been made on the noncovalent binding ability of transition metal complexes with DNA to understand the principles of DNA recognition^{14–22}. A number of results have indicated that transition metal complexes have the ability to selectively recognize specific DNA sequences and conformations^{14,19}. For example, biologically less important simple octahedral amine complexes, Co(NH₃)₆³⁺ and Co(en)₃³⁺, bind in the major groove of DNA in both a sequence and DNA structure selective manner^{14,19,22}. It has also been reported that Co(NH₃)₆³⁺ and Δ -Co(en)₃³⁺ can selectively interact with DNA by forming hydrogen bonds with the N7 and O6 groups of two adjacent guanines in the major groove^{14,19,23} whereas square planar peptide complexes of Ni^{II} selectively associate with A/T regions in the minor groove²⁴. However, depending on the specific DNA sequence these non-intercalating complexes are capable of inducing DNA conformational transitions from *B*-type DNA to either *Z*- or *A*-type DNA²⁵. The shape and symmetry of a metal complex in relation to DNA binding site are considered to be the predominant factors.

Two self-complementary dodecanucleotides d(CAATCCGGATTG) and d(TCGGGATCCCGA) were designed to contain both GG and AT sequences with the former containing a central GG sequence and two potential A/T rich binding regions and the latter contains only a single

AT sequence flanked by G/C regions²⁶. ¹H NMR study of binding of Pt(en)₂²⁺ with these two dodecanucleotides demonstrated that square planar Pt(en)₂²⁺ complex does not bind GG sequences or in the major groove but selectively binds at AT sequence in the DNA minor groove²⁶.

3. Kinetics and mechanism

(i) Complexation of [Pt(dien)(H₂O)]²⁺ with nucleobases :

Nucleobases are considered to be the main target of anticancer platinum drugs in cellular DNA. It has been reported that platinum(II) exhibits a strong affinity to bind 6-oxopurine nucleosides through the N7 ring nitrogen in acidic medium although at higher pH coordination to the more basic N1 position become possible upon deprotonation of N1H. Ritala and Arpalahiti²⁷ studied the kinetics of complexation of [Pt(dien)(H₂O)]²⁺ (dien = diethylenetriamine) with N1 and N7-methylated guanosines as models to simulate the binding abilities of these sites of guanine bases of DNA with platinum complexes. The rate data and HPLC traces of mixtures corresponded to N7 bound 1 : 1 complex for 1-MeGuo (1-methylguanosine) and N1-bound 1 : 1 complex for 7-MeGuo (7-methylguanosine) and 7-MeIno (7-methylinosine). Similarly the reaction of N(9)-substituted guanine with platinum complexes indicated that N(7) atom is the preferred site for metal binding. A number of complexes containing this ligand were identified. Deprotonation of the nucleobase at N(1) position (pK_a = 9.4)²⁸ makes a second metal binding site available for formation of N(1), N(7) diplatinated guanine adducts. Furthermore, coordination at N(7) site increases the nucleophilicity of the N(3) atom thereby resulting three preferential binding sites N(1), N(3), and N(7) in selected conditions²⁷.

At autogeneous pH, a stable bis adduct, *cis*-[(PMe₃)₂Pt(9-MeGu)₂]²⁺ is formed in the reaction of *cis*-[(PMe₃)₂Pt(H₂O)₂]²⁺ with nucleobases like cytosine and N(9)-substituted guanine and also cytosine²⁹. At neutral pH, the aqua complex is converted to dinuclear species *cis*-[(PMe₃)₂Pt(μ-OH)₂]²⁺ and a variety of oligomers of general formula *cis*-[(PMe₃)₂Pt(9-MeGu(-H))]_nⁿ⁺ from which the stable cyclic hexamer, *cis*-[(PMe₃)₂Pt(9-MeGu(-H))]₆⁶⁺ was crystallized as a pure compound²⁹.

(ii) Reaction of chloro- and aqua(diethylethriamine)-platinum(II) with model nucleosides :

The (*cis/trans*)-diammine-diaqua complexes are accepted as the predominant species for reaction with DNA. Similar observation has also been confirmed in the reaction of *cis*platin with leucineaminopeptidase³⁰, γ -glutamyl transpeptidase^{30,31}, and albumin³². In the reaction of *cis*platin with *S*-containing biomolecules the results are

complex³³. The S-containing biomolecules are considered to be important due to their tendency to develop resistance, inactivation, and may reduce high toxicity of *cis*platin.

Two platinum complexes, [Pt(dien)Cl]Cl and [Pt(dien)H₂O]Cl₂, containing nonremovable tridentate ligand (dien) were considered to be useful model for understanding the first binding step of platinum antitumor compounds with DNA. The kinetics and mechanism of complexation of these two platinum complexes with glutathione (GSH), its derivative S-methyl glutathione (GS-Me), and guanosine 5'-monophosphate was investigated³³. Rate constant data indicated that [Pt(dien)Cl]⁺ reacted more rapidly with GSH and GS-Me whereas 5'-GMP had strong kinetic preference for [Pt(dien)(H₂O)]²⁺ over GSH and GS-Me. The rate determining step for the reaction of 5'-GMP with [Pt(dien)Cl]⁺ is the formation of [Pt(dien)(H₂O)]²⁺, followed by a rapid nucleophilic substitution of the aqua ligand by 5'-GMP through its N7 atom; GSH and GS-Me, however, substituted the bound Cl⁻ without the intervention of the aqua intermediate. This study also indicated that steric crowding in the planar complex retarded the rate of ligand substitution. It was suggested that some model compounds having similar rate of aquation as that of *cis*platin and geometry not favoring direct attack by S-containing biomolecules might possess improved antitumor activity and lower toxicity³³.

(iii) *Complexation of trans-[PtCl₂(NH₃)₂] with model nucleobases :*

The kinetics and mechanism of complexation of *trans*platin with the purine nucleoside inosine was studied to simulate the reactions of this isomer with DNA and to understand the differential behavior in anticancer activities of both *cis*platin and *trans*platin. It has been reported that both these isomers bind bifunctionally to DNA and the *trans* isomer inhibits replication to the same extent as the *cis* isomer³⁴. Since platinum(II) is an inert metal ion, the differential activity of these isomers might arise from kinetic factors³⁵. Mikola and Arpalahti investigated the kinetics and mechanism of complexation of *trans*platin with the model nucleobases³⁶.

Comparison of rate data indicates the importance of *trans* effect in the reactivity of platinum(II)³⁷. It has been postulated that the Cl⁻ hydrolysis of *trans* isomer is almost completely prevented in plasma because of high concentration of Cl⁻ in plasma. The most striking difference in biological activities of the *cis* and *trans* isomers may partly be due to markedly differential properties of the diaqua species of these isomers. The first hydrolysis products are usually considered as active intermediates for DNA

binding. At cellular pH (~7.4) both *cis*- and *trans*-(chloro)-(aqua)(NH₃)₂platinum(II) species bind nucleobases at comparable rates³⁶.

Arpalahti³⁸ investigated the pH dependent complexation of *cis*-(diaqua)(diammine)platinum(II) with inosine and 1-methylinosine. The kinetic and HPLC data indicated formation of both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes and 1-MeIno forms only N7-coordinated platinum complexes. It is reported that aquated *cis*-(NH₃)₂platinum(II) forms dimers and higher aggregates in neutral solution through OH bridges. These complexes are inert toward substitution and intermediates by partial replacement of aqua ligand with nucleosides were suggested. He also reported that because of availability of multiple binding sites in inosine, the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes become complicated³⁸.

Arpalahti³⁸ proposed that the aqua ligand of *cis*-(diaqua)(NH₃)₂platinum(II) is replaced by the nucleoside and hydroxo group is inactive toward substitution reaction. The ability of complexation of diaqua species is ~10 times higher than that of aqua-hydroxo species. It has been reported that N7 is the predominant binding site for complexation for 1-MeIno and it only forms N7-bound complexes where as the complexation of inosine becomes very complicated due to its multiple binding sites (N1H and N7H). The coordination of second ligand to the N7-bound 1 : 1 complex of inosine is facilitated by the deprotonation of N1H with a concomitant proton attachment to the deprotonated OH group in the platinum moiety.

Mikola and Arpalahti³⁹ also extended kinetics and mechanistic study to the complexation of *trans*-(diaqua)(diammine)platinum(II) with some model nucleobases to understand their differential reactivities and/or simulate the binding modes with DNA.

(a) *Complexation with 1-methylinosine* : The reactions of diaqua Pt^{II} species with 1-methylinosine in excess yielded a dominant 1 : 1 complex and a 1 : 2 complex, the base is coordinated to N7 site in both complexes. 1-MeIno acts as a neutral ligand (pK_a = 1.39) in the pH range 2.92–5.14, the complexation pathway in the presence of excess 1-MeIno is depicted in Scheme 1³⁹.

Scheme 1

(b) *Complexation with inosine* : HPLC traces of the reactions of *trans*-(diaqua)(diammine)platinum(II) with inosine indicated formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes below pH < 5.5. These data also suggested that preferable coordination site is N7 of inosine. But at high pH (> 5.5), three additional products are reported; these are identified as 1 : 1 and two 1 : 2 complexes where 1 : 2 complexes are formed through coordination of N1 and N7 sites and N1 sites only (pH > 7.8) of inosine³⁹.

(iv) *Reaction with amino acids and its analogues* :

The kinetics and mechanism of reactions of *trans*-diamminediaquaplatinum(II), with some amino acids and its analogues were reported. Multinuclear NMR spectroscopic data indicated that the reaction of (methylimino)diacetic acid (midaH₂) with *cis*-diamminediaquaplatinum(II) yielded a linear type *O*-bonded complex, followed by rapid ring closure to the thermodynamically stable five-membered *N,O*-chelate complex⁴⁰. Similarly, both a five-membered *N,O*- and a six-membered *O,O*-chelates of Pt^{II} are reported in the reaction of 2-aminomalonic acid with *cis*-diamminediaquaplatinum(II)⁴¹. Appleton *et al.*⁴⁰ studied the reactions of 2-aminomalonic acid (amalH₂) and its analogues L-aspartic acid (aspH₂), L-glutamic acid (gluH₂) with *cis*-diamminediaquaplatinum(II) and ¹⁹⁵Pt NMR data indicated that the products are a mixture of five-membered (*N,O*) chelates i.e. [Pt(¹⁵NH₃)₂(glu-N,O)]⁺ (~75%), and [Pt(¹⁵NH₃)₂(amal-N,O)] (~25%) and there was no evidence of a six-membered *O,O*-chelate complex. Similar results have been reported for the reaction of *trans*-diamminediaquaplatinum(II) with aspartic acid and glutamic acid; NMR data are consistent with the formation of a five-membered *N, αO*-chelate with no detectable amount of the *O,O*-chelate with six/seven-membered ring⁴⁰.

The reaction of *N,O*-chelates with excess of *cis*-diamminediaquaplatinum(II) resulted in the formation of multinuclear chelates. In the case of amal, facile anation of [Pt(NH₃)₂(H₂O)₂]²⁺ to [{Pt(NH₃)₂]₂(amal)]²⁺ has been reported. This is an example of "Opportunistic" coordination of a weak donor atom (to platinum) that is positioned favourably through the steric constraints imposed by stronger ligands bound to the metal⁴⁰. These results highlight the stereochemical consequences favouring interaction of biomolecules with platinum.

(v) *Formation of oxo and Pt⁰ complexes* :

It has been reported that the reactions of (carbonato)(diphosphino)platinum(II) with substrates such as CO and phosphine led to Pt⁰ species and oxidized substrates. Andrews *et al.*⁴² proposed a plausible mechanism in which platinum oxo phosphonium intermediates were formed by

interaction of the added phosphine with one of the carbonate oxygen atoms.

(vi) *Oxidation of SO₂ by platinum complexes* :

Koshy and Harris⁴³ investigated the kinetics and mechanism of the reactions of aquapentaaamineplatinum(IV) with sulfite. The oxygen bonded sulfite complex, [Pt(NH₃)₅(OSO₂)]²⁺ was identified kinetically which was formed by addition of SO₂ and HSO₃⁻ to the Pt-OH bond obeying the rate law : rate = {k₁[SO₂] + k₂[HSO₃⁻]}[Pt(NH₃)₅OH³⁺]; k₁(k₂) = 6.8 × 10⁶ (5.9 × 10²) dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ at 25°C. The *O*-bonded sulfite complex, [Pt(NH₃)₅(OSO₂)]SO₃·2H₂O was also isolated by them in solid state. This complex in excess sulfite, however, undergoes loss of *cis*-NH₃ to yield *cis*-[Pt(NH₃)₄(SO₃)₂], the kinetic characteristics of which suggests that there is a rapid *cis*-NH₃ replacement by H₂O followed by rate limiting sulfite ligand isomerisation (*O*- to *S*-) : (k = 4.0 × 10⁻⁵ s⁻¹) followed by rapid replacement of the *cis*-aqua ligand by sulfite. These sulfite ligand isomerisation is similar to those reported for several other cobalt(III), chromium(III) and rhodium(III) aqua-amine complexes⁴⁴. The disulfite complex also undergoes internal electron transfer at elevated temperature to a Pt^{II} complex, [Pt(NH₃)₃(SO₃)] and the process is catalysed by H⁺.

Elding *et al.*⁴⁵ studied the oxidation of SO₂·nH₂O/HSO₃⁻/SO₃²⁻ by Pt(CN)₄Cl₂²⁻ and proposed that the stoichiometry of the reaction is 1 : 1 consistent with the reaction : Pt(CN)₄Cl₂²⁻ + HSO₃⁻ + H₂O → Pt(CN)₄²⁻ + 2Cl⁻ + HSO₄⁻ + H₂O. It has been proposed that [Pt(CN)₄Cl₂]²⁻ is reduced by both HSO₃⁻ and SO₃²⁻ in the range of 0.3 < pH < 4.5. The kinetic parameters suggest that the incoming nucleophiles attack the coordinated chloride, followed by inner-sphere two-electron transfer to the metal center and formation of Pt(CN)₄²⁻, ClSO₃H and ClSO₃⁻; rapid hydrolysis of chlorosulphuric acid and chlorosulfate(VI) occurs to form HSO₄⁻. The reaction of [Pt(CN)₄ClOH]²⁻ with HSO₃⁻ conforms to a three step process. First step is the very rapid formation of *O*-bonded sulfite complex, [Pt(CN)₄Cl(OSO₂)]³⁻, followed by second step considered to be the rate-determining step in which intramolecular isomerization takes place i.e. the *O*-bonded complex isomerizes to thermodynamically relatively more stable *S*-bonded complex, [Pt(CN)₄Cl(SO₃)]³⁻. In the third step, the *S*-bonded isomer rapidly reduces to Pt(CN)₄²⁻ and HSO₄⁻ in an inner-sphere two-electron transfer process.

4. Luminescence properties

Synthesis and study of luminescent properties of transition metal complexes have attracted considerable attention because these complexes exhibit fundamental properties

with potential applications in different branches of chemistry including photochemistry, photophysics, chemiluminescence, electrochemiluminescence, and electron transfer reactions⁴⁶. Moreover, these complexes have been reported to be useful in solar energy conversion processes, as labels for specific sites in polymeric arrays, and in general biological systems. Excited state electronic spectral studies of d^8 square planar complexes were reported for $\text{MLL}'-(\text{mnt})_n^-$ ($n = 1, \text{M} = \text{Ir, Rh}; n = 0, \text{M} = \text{Pt}; \text{L}, \text{L}' = \text{PR}_3, \text{P}(\text{OR})_3, \text{CO}; \text{mnt} = \text{maleonitriledithiolate}$)⁴⁷, orthometalated Pt^{II} arylpyridine complexes⁴⁸, $\text{Ir}(\text{bis}(\text{diphenylphosphino})\text{ethane})_2^+$ and related analogues⁴⁹, $\text{Ir}(\text{dien})(\text{diimine})^+$ systems⁵⁰, $\text{Pt}(\text{biphenyl})(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_2$ ⁵¹, and $\text{Pt}(\text{diimine})(\text{dithiolate})$ complexes⁵². A few d^8 square planar metal complexes, $[\text{Pt}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)(\text{CO})(5\text{-AQ})]$, $[\text{Pt}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)(\text{CO})(9\text{-AA})]$, $[\text{Pt}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2(5\text{-AQ})_2]$ ($5\text{-AQ} = 5\text{-aminoquinoline}$, $9\text{-AA} = 9\text{-aminoacridine}$) exhibit this property in solution at room temperature⁵³. These complexes also exhibit luminescence properties in rigid matrix at 77 K from the lowest lying singlet $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ excited state. A partial charge transfer has also been reported in the (emitter) excited state for $[\text{Pt}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)(\text{CO})(5\text{-AQ})]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2(5\text{-AQ})_2]$.

Rillema *et al.*⁵⁴ reported that platinum complexes are divided into 4 types depending on their emitting states: (i) intraligand (IL) $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ emitters, for example, platinum(II) complexes of 8-quinolinol chelates, a $[\text{Pt}(5,5'\text{-dimethyl-2,2'\text{-bipyridine}})(\text{CN})_2]$ adduct⁵⁵, and a $[\text{Pt}(2,2'\text{-bipyridine})(\text{NH}_3)_2]^{2+}$ -dibenzo[30] crown-10-adduct⁵⁶; (ii) interligand (ILCT) $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ emitters, for example, platinum(II)-dithiolate-diimine complexes⁵⁷; (iii) the $d\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ (metal-to-ligand; MLCT) emitters, for example, $[\text{Pt}(\text{diimine})(\text{biphenyl})]$ complexes⁵⁸ and platinum(II) complexes containing 2-phenylpyridine and 2-(2-thionyl)pyridine ligands⁵⁹; (iv) metal-metal excited state emitters, for example, $[\text{Pt}_2(\text{P}_2\text{O}_5\text{H}_2)_4]$ ⁶⁰, $[\text{Pt}(\text{CN})_4]_n^{2-}$ ⁶¹, $\text{Pt}_2[\text{bis}(\text{diphenylphosphino})\text{methane}]_2(\text{CN})_4$ ⁶² and an excimer based on $[\text{Pt}(4,7\text{-diphenyl-1,10-phenanthroline})(\text{CN})_2]$ ⁶³.

$[\text{Pt}(\text{trpy})\text{X}]^+$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl, NCS, OMe, OH}$, $\text{trpy} = 2,2':6',2''\text{-terpyridine}$) complexes exhibit several metal to ligand CT absorption bands in the visible and near UV regions of the spectrum⁶⁴. The thiocyanate, hydroxide, and methoxide derivatives exhibit luminescence at room temperature in acetonitrile solution and the emission is a $^3d\text{-}\pi^*$ CT state based on broad band shape, modest solvent dependence and lack of concentration dependent properties.

Gray *et al.*⁶⁵ reported that the electronic spectrum of $[\text{Pt}(\text{trpy})\text{Cl}]^+$ is influenced dramatically by intermolecular stacking interactions in solution and in the solid state. The low temperature solid-state luminescence of $[\text{Pt}(\text{trpy})\text{Cl}]^+$

is assigned to a $^3(\text{MMLCT})$ (metal-metal-to-ligand charge transfer) transition and energy of this band is highly dependent on the counter ion ($\text{PF}_6^-, \text{ClO}_4^-, \text{Cl}^-, \text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3^-$). It has also been reported that the red perchlorate salt exhibits a relatively narrow emission at 725 nm but consistent with a $^3(\text{MMLCT})$ transition, the orange ($\text{ClO}_4^-, \text{Cl}^-, \text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3^-$) and yellow ($[\text{Pt}(\text{trpy})\text{Cl}]^+$) salts have displayed extremely broad room-temperature emission bands. Grey assigned this type of luminescence to an excimeric intraligand transitions resulting from $\pi\text{-}\pi$ interactions and proposed that the temperature dependent emission from the orange and yellow solid materials originate from multiple electronic states.

Eisenberg *et al.*⁶⁶ synthesized a series of square planar diphosphine dithiolate complexes of platinum(II) where diphosphine ligands include dppe (1,2-bis(diphenylphosphino)ethane), dppv (1,2-bis(diphenylphosphino)ethylene), dppb (1,2-bis(diphenylphosphino)benzene), chpe (1,2-bis(dicyclohexylphosphino)ethane), dppm (bis(diphenylphosphino)methane), pumpum (1,2-bis(dimethoxyphosphino)ethane), PPh_3 (triphenylphosphine), PMe_2Ph (dimethylphenyl phosphine), PCy_3 (tricyclohexylphosphine), $\text{P}(\text{OPh})_3$ (triphenylphosphite), $\text{P}(\text{O-i-Pr})_3$ (triisopropyl phosphite), and dithiolate ligands are mnt (maleonitriledithiolate), ecda (1-(ethoxycarbonyl)-1-cyanoethylene-2,2-dithiolate). These complexes exhibit strong emission in the solid state and in frozen glass at 77 K with structured spectra for mnt complexes and broad and featureless for ecda complexes.

It has been reported that some platinum complexes have long lived excited states and/or exhibit room temperature luminescence in fluid solution and appear to have ligand centered i.e. intraligand excited states. Electronic spectral data of the platinum(II) linear-chain containing complexes have demonstrated that the maxima of the lowest absorption and emission bands display strong dependence on the intrachain metal-metal separation⁶⁷.

5. Ligand isomerism and stacking in square planar platinum complexes

Platinum complexes display isomerism and polychromism. One such example is bis-thiocyanate complexes of platinum(II)⁶⁸. It displays unusual chemical and physical properties in which two coordination sites are occupied by a bidentate ligand forcing the pseudohalide ligands to occupy the *cis* positions. The nature of the bidentate ligand influences the type of bonding of the pseudohalide ligands and the solvation of the solids. Burmeister⁶⁹ reported that there are 10 indistinguishable modes of coordination in which the SCN group can bond to a metal including ionic, simple covalent, bridging, linear, and bent mode formation.

Out of these 10 modes M-SCN and M-NCS ligation are most fundamental in understanding the interactions between platinum. Herber reported that the bis-thiocyanate complex of Pt(bpy) exist in two isomeric forms i.e. a yellow complex soluble in a variety of solvents which transforms under relatively mild conditions to a insoluble and stable red polymeric species. FTIR and NMR spectroscopic data indicated that the yellow complex contains two *cis* S-bonded SCN ligands where as in the red insoluble complex the SCN ligands have "flipped" to become N-bonded. EXAFS data suggested the presence of two Pt-Pt distances in the red solid, one of which point to the formation of stacked square planar Pt moieties. Similarly, FTIR, ^{13}C and ^{15}N MAS NMR spectroscopic data of Pt-(dmbp)(CSN) $_2$ indicated that it contains three isomers⁷⁰: (i) kinetically favored -(SCN) $_2$ form, (ii) -(SCN)(NCS) form, and (iii) thermodynamically favored -(NCS) $_2$ form. Pt-L $_3$ EXAFS data indicated presence of Pt-Pt interactions in solid (iii) form. This is indicative of ligand isomerism, mixed isomerism, and stacking in this square planar platinum(II) complexes.

6. Conclusion

cis-Diamminedichloroplatinum(II) and carboplatin are used as potent anticancer drugs exhibiting remarkable activity against various carcinoma cell lines. Their drug resistance and severe toxic side effects remain their limitation. Thus, synthesis and characterization of novel platinum based antitumor drugs with an overall broader spectrum of activity and reduced toxicity is a challenging area of bioinorganic chemistry. In addition to this further research activity on substitution reactions of platinum complexes using biomolecules as ligands and search for novel platinum complexes for photophysical studies need to be pursued in the years ahead.

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